

exercise blood lactate (BLa), ratings of perceived exertion (RPE), the frequency of boxing-specific actions and total punch accelerations were recorded during both trials to characterise the internal and external demands. Ten participants also engaged in bouts of competitive sparring (contested over the same durations and instructed to compete realistically) 5–9 days later to provide a source of validation data for these demands. The BOXFIT yielded mean and peak HR of 169 ± 11 and 188 ± 11 beats $\cdot$ min⁻¹, respectively, VO_2 of 41 ± 6 ml $\cdot$ kg $\cdot$ min⁻¹, BLa of 4.6 ± 1.3 mmol $\cdot$ L⁻¹, RPE 6–8 across rounds and punch accelerations of 2737 ± 104 g. Typically, values for all measures increased ($P < 0.01$) from one round to the next (e.g., mean HR; ES [95% CI] = 0.64 [0.1 to 1.17], 0.28 [-0.80 to 0.25] for round one vs. two and two vs. three, respectively). Of these, the mean and peak HR, post-exercise BLa and RPE represented $96 \pm 4\%$, $97 \pm 4\%$, $49 \pm 10\%$ and $90 \pm 13\%$ of sparring values, respectively. The coefficient of variation for measurements was found to be 2–12%. The findings reflect that whilst the boxers experienced a high internal demand, the simulation protocol yielded responses typically lower than those observed during competitive sparring. Nonetheless, the responses to the BOXFIT were sufficiently reliable that, with slight modifications (i.e., alterations to its external load), applied sports scientists, coaches and boxers could adopt the simulation to appraise systematic changes or improve features of boxing performance.

D2.S2.3(3). Influence of team cohesion in sport in school-aged students: in relation to gender, age and type of sport

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Team cohesion provides greater learning, more satisfaction in sport and with team mates, more productivity, better communications, more feelings of security and greater adherence to the sports practice (Eys, Loughhead, Bray, and Carron, 2009, *The Sport Psychologist*, 23, 330–345). Therefore, the main purpose of this study was to analyse the state of team cohesion in school-aged students practising sports, as a function of gender, age and type of sport. The research used a *descriptive quantitative* methodology by means of a questionnaire. The sample consisted of 816 subjects (50.3% male and 49.7% female) of between 12 and 18 years of

age (mean 14.6, $s = 1.9$), who practise different individual and team sports in the Castilla-La Mancha region. Several aspects were taken into account for the statistical calculations: the population is infinite; thus for the population variance we used the most unfavourable supposition where “P” and “Q” are equal with 50% each; the confidence interval was set at 95.5%, with a margin of error of $\pm 3.5\%$. The Psychological Characteristics related to Sports Performance questionnaire (Características Psicológicas relacionadas con el Rendimiento Deportivo (CPRD)) with Cronbach alpha of $r = .85$ was used. The results show that with regard to gender there were no significant differences in team cohesion in any of the items analysed, $t(814) = -1.71$, $P > 0.05$; $t(814) = -1.66$, $P > 0.05$, coinciding with previous studies (e.g., Paradis and Loughhead, 2010, *International Journal of Sports*, 41, 1–20). With regard to age, the younger sports practitioners (12–13 years) revealed a lower level of cohesion than the older ones (14–15 years), $F(2, 538.22) = 3.78$, $P < 0.05$, again coinciding with other previous studies (e.g., Subramanyam, 2013, *International Journal of Sports Sciences & Fitness*, 3, 250–258). With respect to different sports, there were statistically significant differences between the students who practised volleyball, who showed a stronger team spirit, and those who practised tennis $F(9, 326.19) = 4.53$, $P < 0.05$, again in line with previous research (e.g., Halbrook et al., 2012, *Journal of Sport Behavior*, 35, 61–77). The results suggest the need to promote team cohesion in school-aged sports people as it has been shown that this type of training provides the young sports person with a greater degree of commitment to their team. The team cohesion variable is particularly relevant in team sports (or in individual sports when playing doubles or as a team).

D2.S2.3(4). Between- and within-race variance in elite short-track speed skating: a new approach to analyse group behaviour during competition

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Previous research indicated that short-track speed skaters seem to alter their pacing behaviour based on their opponents, especially during the initial stages of 1500 m races (Konings et al., 2015, *International Journal of Sport Physiology and Performance*, doi: 10.1123/ijsp.2015-0137). The aim of the present study was to gain more insight into the interaction of